

Simulation Design of 542kWp DC/480kWp AC Solar Photovoltaic System at Institute of Southern Punjab

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Abstract

Conventional methods of producing electricity are expensive, pollute the environment, need a lot of maintenance, and eventually run out of power. Because of this, it is imperative to make use of the unrealized potential of renewable energy sources that are also ecologically beneficial. At the Institute of Southern Punjab (ISP), Multan, Pakistan, geographical location coordinates latitude 30° 17' 20" N and longitude 71° 30' 1" E. Current study developed an effective, long-lasting, and environmentally friendly Grid Tie PV System (GTPVS) to address this issue. One location where solar energy has enormous promise is Multan. At this location, the average yearly horizontal solar irradiance is 1861.8 kWh/m²/year, and the average diffuse horizontal solar irradiance is 898.9 kWh/m²/year. In this study, 'PVSyst Software' is used to calculate the performance ratio and various power losses, such as inverter, temperature-related losses, and losses from PV modules. Every day, 3026.26 kg of coal is saved, which is the same as growing 29062.87 Teak trees for a lifetime. According to the National Electric Power Regulation Authority (NEPRA) rule Tarif A3(66) is applied to universities and schools, where 60 Rs/kWh is a unit cost in the year 2024. The generated energy cost for the 'Longi Solar Cell' for the proposed location in ISP Multan, is 0.07 US dollars per kWh, while the standard energy pricing in Pakistan in 2024 is 0.21 US dollars per kWh. The simulation results show that the proposed Roof-Top Solar Photovoltaic System (RTSPVS) design energy production is 966.4 MWh/year. The Annual Performance Ratio (PR) for the proposed system is 85.8%.

Index Terms: Grid Tie PV System, Green Energy / Solution, Photovoltaic Power, PVSyst Software, Roof-Top Solar Photovoltaic System.

I. INTRODUCTION

The conditions in Pakistan's energy zone are appalling. Our exclusive reliance on conventional energy sources during the preceding 20 years is the main reason for the current electricity shortfall. Currently, switching to renewable energy sources is the only solution to resolve energy-related problems. In this sense, one of the finest renewable energy sources that is widely accessible to nations like Pakistan is solar energy. Installing Solar Photovoltaic (PV) systems is a green endeavor. Nearly everything on the planet has enough solar energy, which is also free. Furthermore, as compared to other traditional sources, the running cost of Solar systems is quite cheap as compared to other conventional power generation options in renewable systems like Magneto Hydro Dynamic (MHD) power generation, Hydro Power Plant, and Wind Power Generation [1-3]. In order to aid in the development of various renewable energy system plans, several Solar cell module systems were addressed [4], and [5]. After a thorough detail of the comparative grid tie system and solar system a techno-economic feasibility study was carried out to aid in the analysis of the most cost-effective renewable

energy system in different areas of Pakistan [6], and [7]. For household load systems different optimization techniques of standalone PV and Wind systems are evaluated [8-10].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pakistan, a growing nation, is experiencing load shedding as a result of insufficient power generation throughout the nation [11-14]. The endeavor to switch all of the nation's educational institutions to renewable energy sources has been started by the government [15], and [16]. According to Khan et al. (2024), Pakistan's grid-connected power system is among the finest in the SAARC region due to its high solar and photovoltaic system irradiation. Building energy systems are also used in Multan, one of the country's most populous cities [17], and [18]. The national standard for these kinds of programs is set by this research. This document provides location data in real-time for specific areas of Pakistan based on simulation findings. The primary goal is to generate power through a Roof-Top Solar Photovoltaic System (RTSPVS) of green and clean energy to fulfill daily usage of the load requirements of the Academic block of the Institute of Southern Punjab Multan

Pakistan, in place of the conventional electricity sourced from Water & Power Development Authority (WAPDA). Using the PVSyst software, simulation design of solar cell and PV system inverter for the ‘Academic Block of ISP’ Multan and others, also each component is examined for the optimized power generation. It is also necessary to analyze and study the changes in the actual solar plant's environmental and economic circumstances over time. The outcomes of the suggested PV system and the traditional energy supply system of Pakistan are also compared. This research is useful for installing a solar system as an RTSPVS on the 6th block of the ISP since load values are real goods used in the building of ISP Multan.

This research paper is structured as: The RTSPVS of Academic block for installing solar cell systems is provided in Section II. In Section III, the modeling of a renewable energy system with PVSyst will be demonstrated. The suggested system findings are presented in Section IV, which also includes a discussion of the comparison research. The conclusion and suggestions for the future will be emphasized in the end i.e., Section V and Section VI.

Figure I: Proposed Area of RTSPVS Installation

III. SITE PARAMETERS AND SYSTEM MODELING

Multan, the biggest city in southern Punjab, is home to Multan Electric Power Company (MEPCO), Pakistan's largest power distribution company in terms of customers. Because the Institute of Southern Punjab Multan's Academic block requires power throughout the day and sun availability almost throughout the year, the Academic block geographic coordinates are 30.29°N and 71.50°E. The proposed location is perfect for solar power generation, which makes it the ideal location for installing and producing solar energy to fulfill its needs and sell it to the market in order to make some money. The potential locations for the RTSPVS installation are depicted in figure I. The area of the top floor of the Engineering and Technology Academic block is within the red line representing the 22,839 m² where our proposed PV system can be installed easily.

Module area for solar irradiation collection required 2520 m², each unit nominal power is 550 W_p, overall, 586 strings×17 series total 986 modules required for 542 kW_p DC power generation by using Longi Solar cell model LR5-72 HPH 550 M. Inverter model SG80KTL is used with nominal power conversion of each unit is 80 kW_{ac}, total 6 number of inverters are used for the 480 kW_{ac} power conversion. The solar pathways at the location chosen for the solar system installation with a tilt angle of 30° and azimuth angle of 0° for an entire year. Table I also includes the calculations and presentation of the location's other significant metrics and variables. Without a doubt, the proposed location has been chosen to maximize its solar energy potential. Average annual direct solar radiation is 4.85 kWh/m² per day, and diffuse solar irradiation is 2.49 kWh/m² per day, this not only supplies the electricity needed for the Academic block but also feeds electricity into the grid to greatly boost the growth of the national economy.

Figure II: Load Requirement of Proposed System (9:00 AM-4:00 PM)

Table I: Theoretical Framework of Attributes [7]

Month	Direct Irradiation (kWh/m ² /month)	Diffuse Irradiation (kWh/m ² /month)	Global Incident (kWh/m ² /month)	Global Effective (kWh/m ² /month)	Temperature (°C)	Wind Velocity (m/sec)	Relative Humidity (%)
January	102.8	42.3	148.0	146.3	10.94	1.00	73.9
February	116.3	52.4	149.6	147.7	15.32	1.41	68.6
March	159.1	72.7	183.1	180.3	21.42	1.49	59.8
April	183.0	84.9	188.6	185.5	27.22	1.70	43.3
May	200.8	101.2	190.6	187.0	32.71	1.90	38.2
June	193.8	107.6	178.0	174.7	32.36	1.90	52.9
July	191.3	112.4	177.9	174.5	31.25	1.60	72.1
August	187.9	101.8	186.4	183.3	30.43	1.29	75.5
September	170.5	74.0	188.7	185.9	28.28	1.19	73.1
October	144.5	63.3	178.8	176.6	24.68	0.90	62.8
November	116.7	43.9	166.3	164.3	17.84	0.80	64.8
December	95.1	42.4	140.3	138.6	12.94	0.80	70.8
Yearly	1861.8	898.9	2076.3	2044.6	23.82	1.3	63.0

Figure III: Solar Path of RTSPVS at ISP Multan

Figure II, above shows the load requirement of Academic block of ISP Multan for day time from 9:00 AM to 4:00 PM. The location's sun path is shown in figure III. This figure idealizes the longest and shortest days at the suggested location in terms of solar exposure hours. 30° is the chosen tilted angle, and 0° is the ultimate azimuth angle.

IV. SYSTEM MODELING

Figure IV, describes the working of the whole RTSPVS that involves the Solar PV, Utility grid, and Grid Connected Inverter (GCI) for better import and export of power to fulfill the demand of load.

Figure IV: Working of RTSPVS

V. SUMMARY RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table I gives the geographical location data which is essential for the grid tie system design and modeling. For PV system design solar irradiance potential and sun path facing solar module arrangement, both contribute significantly to the production of PV energy. PR recorded 85.8% and produced an energy of 966.4 MWh/year. Low temperature improves the solar cell efficiency; the annual average ambient temperature recorded for the proposed location is 23.82 °C.

$$\text{Total Specific Production} = \frac{\text{Energy Production}}{\text{Array Nominal Array Power}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Total Specific Production} = \frac{966400\text{kWh}}{542\text{kWp}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Annual Specific Production} = 1782 \text{ kWh/kWp/year} \quad (3)$$

Power production ranges from 69.93MWh in December to 87.22MWh in April, which is the greatest energy generated. In April, direct solar irradiation was 183.0 kWh/m²; and diffuse solar irradiation received on the proposed cell was 84.9 kWh/m² moderate temperature was 27.22°C recorded, available energy produced by the solar array was 87.22 MWh, energy supplied to the Academic block is 87.83 MWh. The overall contribution of solar energy in the month of April is 70.11 MWh and energy import from the grid is 17.72 MWh, whereas energy injected into the grid is 16.09 MWh. The performance ratio for the month of April is

recorded at 84.3%. The solar photovoltaic array has produced 966.4 MWh of electricity in total. The system's overall PR is 85.8%, which fulfills the daily load demand and enough energy supply to the grid. Annually average of 1861.8 kWh/m² of direct irradiation falls on the module area of the collector plane.

A. Performance Ratio

The proposed RTSPVS in ISP Multan produced an annual PR of 85.8%. The PR varied during the year, reaching a maximum of 91.1% in January and a minimum of 82.4% in May as depicted in figure V and table II. The PR derived using mathematical methods and that received from the PVSyst are almost identical.

$$\text{Performance Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Energy Recorded kWh}}{\text{Energy Obtained}} \quad (4)$$

Figure V: PR of RTSPVS

Table II: Performance Ratio and Injected Energy into Grid

Months	Energy Available at Solar Array (MWh)	Energy Supplied to the User (MWh)	Energy from the Solar (MWh)	Extra Energy Export to the Grid (MWh)	Energy Import from the Grid (MWh)	Performance Ratio (%)
January	74.00	90.76	65.75	7.37	25.01	0.911
February	73.18	81.97	62.97	9.34	19.01	0.891
March	86.97	90.76	71.63	14.34	19.13	0.866
April	87.22	87.83	70.11	16.09	17.72	0.843
May	86.24	90.76	68.11	17.09	22.65	0.824
June	81.33	87.83	64.04	16.30	23.79	0.832
July	82.00	90.76	64.57	16.47	26.19	0.840
August	85.98	90.76	69.23	15.72	21.53	0.840
September	87.10	87.83	70.85	15.23	16.98	0.841
October	83.78	90.76	70.71	12.05	20.05	0.853
November	80.31	87.83	68.98	10.42	18.85	0.881
December	69.93	90.76	62.34	6.77	28.42	0.908
Year	978.03	1068.59	809.27	157.17	259.32	0.858

B. Loss Diagram

The most crucial element that has to be considered during design is power system losses. It is a significant factor in determining the output of power generation.

The total effective irradiation that reaches the solar surface is 2045 kWh/m² when diffuse irradiation is included, but the annual worldwide horizontal irradiation is 1861.8 kWh/m². The PV conversion efficiency of Longi Solar cells at STP is 21.56%. The nominal energy of the array is 1111 MWh, but after accounting for all losses, the available energy at the inverter output is 966.4 MWh. Of this, 809 MWh is directly used annually by the Academic block, and the remaining 157 MWh is injected into the grid to meet the load requirement.

In the event that solar power is unavailable due to clouds or fog, 259 MWh of power is imported from the utility grid. The annual energy loss diagram for the grid-tie system is depicted in figure VII.

C. Daily Input and Output of RTSPVS

Daily input of solar irradiance on PV cells is collected and converted into useful energy in the form of electricity. So daily production of electricity in the form of kWh depends on the input of solar PV cells. In figure VI each dot represents the per day from 1st January to 31st December and on X-axis global irradiance on the incident plane of the solar cell and Y-axis all output of available solar energy of RTSPVS. Overall sketch from the diagram shows that most dots are above 2500 kWh/day, shows the proposed system

can supply this power on a daily basis and solar irradiance availability for the proposed location is above 5 kWh/m² per day which shows the best efficiency for the proposed system for providing power on daily basis. The maximum available energy from solar of RTSPVS is 3000 kWh/day. Overall, this is a feasible system for the required load of the Academic block of ISP Multan. From figure VI anyone can see the feasibility of the proposed system by the dotted concentration is more in the required limits of loads that are dependent on cheap and green solar energy.

In figure VII overall power conversion of the Longi Solar cell is recorded at 21.56% which is one of the best power conversion efficiencies of top-ranked solar cells available in Pakistan, Appropriate solar cell selection is one of the highly beneficial factors for the proposed system. Solar irradiance available on the collector plane is 1862 kWh/m² due to cell efficiency this available irradiance is converted into 1111 MWh on the PV array. The maximum available energy after subtracting all losses on the input of the inverter is 978 MWh. Inverter efficiency losses during operation are recorded at 1.2% and remained energy is 966 MWh which is the peak of available energy of RTSPVS. Furthermore, the remaining available energy at the output of the system that fulfills the demand of the user directly is 809 MWh. Due to the dependency of this system on the availability of sun throughout the year, some days energy required from the utility grid is 259 MWh and surplus energy generation of RTSPVS injected into the grid is 157 MWh as depicted in figure VII.

Figure VI: Daily Input and Output of RTSPVS

Figure VII: Loss Diagram Over the Whole Year

The Institute of Southern Punjab has proposed to install a 542kWp DC/480kWp AC solar photovoltaic system.

Table III: Comparison of Proposed System with Different Studies in South Punjab

Solar PV System	PR (%)	Cost of Energy Unit	Conversion Losses in Inverter
PV Plant Work IUB	83.5	0.11 \$/kWh	0.8%
Quaid-E-Azam Solar Park	79	0.13 \$/kWh	2%
Proposed Work	85.8	0.07 \$/kWh	0.6%

This system has an improved Performance Ratio (PR) and costs less per energy unit than other photovoltaic power plants in the region. As for inverter conversion losses, the proposed site recorded 0.6% losses, which is less than other renewable power parks as depicted in table III.

VI. CONCLUSION

RTSPVS is one of the economical renewable power generation sources that can be installed in city centers and decrease the pollution of cities and the burning of coal in

conventional power plants. Solar energy is one of the finest options for producing electricity since it has the best irradiation in south Punjab, Pakistan. Power generation through renewable energy systems is increasing day by day, among all renewable sources, solar PV systems are in demand at the time not only reducing the line losses of transmission lines by installing RTSPVS in city centers. Current research provides information average yearly and monthly output of energy, different losses that are accountable in RTSPVS, the performance ratio of the system, and solutions to the high cost of unit price and shortage of power even in the day system. The system's highest performance ratio was recorded at 91.1% in the month of January, and the minimum performance ratio was in the month of May at 82.4%. The average performance ratio is 85.8% recorded, and Longi Solar cell power conversion efficiency for the proposed location of ISP Multan is recorded at 21.56%, which is one of the highest power conversion efficiency of solar cells in South Punjab. According to simulation results, RTSPVS is capable of providing 75% of electricity to the Academic block of ISP Multan, and the remaining electricity on cloudy days of winter is imported from the utility grid for continuity in electricity supply. Moreover, the installation of RTSPVS saves 29062.87 Teak trees and 3026.26 kg of coal every day in the production of power generation, it also reduces the CO₂ emission and smog in populated cities of Pakistan. This simulation design of the system helps set up efficient RTSPVS for the production of clean and green power generation.

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Authors Contributions

The authors took all the responsibilities of this research study and equally contributed to the findings.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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